

On the Theory of Persecution

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Abstract : Classification of persecution movement laws is proposed. Modes of persecution in number of specific cases were researched. Modes of movement control using GLONASS/GPS are discussed.

Keywords : UAV Management, mathematical algorithms of targeting and persecution, GLONASS, GPS

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